

Electronic Appendix for "Java Bytecode Normalization for Code Similarity Analysis"

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A Study: Usage of different Java Compilers and Target Levels

To investigate the usage of Java compilers and versions in real-world projects we used the SEART GitHub Search dataset [3], which was created to enable large scale studies on GitHub projects without being limited by the GitHub API usage limitations and contains metadata (but no file contents) for a large amount of repositories hosted on GitHub. We queried the SEART GitHub Search dataset to search for all repositories with Java as main language. This query resulted in 91,113 GitHub repositories containing Java projects. We further limited the dataset for our experiment by only including projects that use Maven [7] as build tool, since it is not as straightforward to determine the used compiler with other build tools. While a Maven build configuration is specified in a static XML-file, a build configuration for Gradle [4], another popular build tool for Java, is dynamically specified in a set of build scripts, which need to be executed to determine the configured compiler. However, executing a Gradle build is a time-consuming task, which fails in many cases [5]. After this filtering step we were left with 29,514 Maven projects, of which we cloned the default branch as of March 2023.

The default way of compiling Maven projects is to invoke the Maven Compiler Plugin [8], which handles all steps related to the compilation. By default the Maven Compiler Plugin uses the compiler of the JDK or OpenJDK installed on the system. However, the Java compiler to be used can be changed by setting the `compilerId` property in the plugin's configuration [9].

To investigate the usage of different compilers in our dataset, we scanned the project's build configuration for this specific property. Due to the SEART GitHub Search dataset only containing repository metadata and the now applying GitHub API limitations, we only scanned the project's root build configuration file. Though it is possible to configure different compilers for certain modules of a project, typically the whole project is compiled with the same compiler that is defined in the project's root build configuration file.

Table 1a shows the results of this experiment. In 99.5% of the projects the default compiler of the JDK installed on the system is used (may be Oracle or some other OpenJDK vendor). There are few instances where the `javac-with-errorprone` compiler, is used. `Javac` only provides an additional command line interface to the default JDK compiler. The other two notable compilers use Eclipse's JDT core compiler for compilation. Note that many of the eclipse compiler usages listed in Table 1a are only part of a debug profile in the build configuration and are therefore only used for debug purposes, as the JDT core compiler

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provides a large set of debug utilities [6]. The projects are still compiled with the default JDK compiler for distribution.

These results show that the vast majority of real-world projects use the JDK's compiler for compilation, there are only few instances in real-world projects in which other compilers are used.

To investigate the usage of Java target levels we used the same process, but scanned the root build configuration file for the properties defining the Java version for compilation, e.g. `source`, `target` or `release` properties [2, 1]. In 79% of all scanned Java projects the target level was explicitly defined. In cases where it is not defined, the default level of the used compiler is utilized. Table 1b shows the usage amount of levels in the investigated projects where it was explicitly defined. More than 50% of projects are configured to use Java 8 as target. Target levels prior to Java 5 or levels in-between Long-Term-Support (LTS) versions are only used sparsely.

Because of these results we limit our normalization on the compilers provided by the JDK and OpenJDK and to Java target levels 5–8, 11 and 17.

■ **Table 1** Compiler and target level usage statistics in Java projects

(a) Compiler		(b) Target level	
Compiler	Amount	Target	Amount
Default JDK	29,355	8	12,260
javac-with-errorprone	63	6	3,550
Eclipse/JDT	48	7	3,287
groovy-eclipse-compiler	35	11	2,063
Others	13	17	871
		5	728
		Others	598

References

- 1 Apache Maven Compiler Plugin - Setting the `-release` of the Java Compiler. Accessed 2023-04-03. URL: <https://maven.apache.org/plugins/maven-compiler-plugin/examples/set-compiler-release.html>.
- 2 Apache Maven Compiler Plugin - Setting the `-source` and `-target` of the Java Compiler. Accessed 2023-04-03. URL: <https://maven.apache.org/plugins/maven-compiler-plugin/examples/set-compiler-source-and-target.html>.
- 3 Ozren Dabic, Emad Aghajani, and Gabriele Bavota. Sampling projects in github for MSR studies. In *18th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Mining Software Repositories, MSR 2021, Madrid, Spain, May 17-19, 2021*, pages 560–564. IEEE, 2021.
- 4 Gradle Build Tool. Accessed 2022-11-07. URL: <https://gradle.org/>.
- 5 Foyzul Hassan, Shaikh Mostafa, Edmund S. L. Lam, and Xiaoyin Wang. Automatic building of java projects in software repositories: A study on feasibility and challenges. In *2017 ACM/IEEE International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement, ESEM 2017, Toronto, ON, Canada, November 9-10, 2017*, pages 38–47. IEEE Computer Society, 2017.
- 6 Eclipse Java development tools (JDT). Accessed 2022-10-17. URL: <https://www.eclipse.org/jdt/core/>.
- 7 Apache Maven Project. Accessed 2023-04-25. URL: <https://maven.apache.org>.

- 8 Apache Maven Compiler Plugin. Accessed 2022-10-25. URL: <https://maven.apache.org/plugins/maven-compiler-plugin/>.
- 9 Apache Maven Compiler Plugin: Using Non-Javac Compilers. Accessed 2022-10-25. URL: <https://maven.apache.org/plugins/maven-compiler-plugin/non-javac-compilers.html>.